

Estimation of Aboveground Carbon Stocks of Kudremukh National Park in the Western Ghats of India using Multi-sensor Remote Sensing Data and Machine Learning Approach

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ABSTRACT

1
2 The Western Ghats of India, a UNESCO World Heritage site and one of the world's eight
3 'hottest hotspots' of biological diversity, are recognized for their highly productive and
4 characteristic montane forest ecosystems. High-resolution and geographically large coverage
5 mapping of forest carbon stocks is valuable to adapt and effectively implement large-scale
6 forest management strategies. Previous approaches to producing maps of carbon stocks at a
7 regional scale have considered limited areal extent and have relied on knowledge-based
8 stratification and regression of plot-level measurements and low-resolution forest vegetation
9 maps derived from active or passive remote sensing data. With an overall aim of near-future
10 applicability to the entire Western Ghats of India, this study investigated the application of a
11 multi-sensor remote sensing technique to estimate aboveground carbon stocks (AGCS) at
12 high spatial resolution in Kudremukh National Park in the Western Ghats. Implementing a
13 feature-fusion-based integration of satellite-based LiDAR (GEDI), SAR (Sentinel-1),
14 multispectral (Sentinel-2) and DEM (SRTM) datasets in a Random Forests machine learning
15 framework, the study proposes a scalable method to map AGB densities and derive carbon
16 stock estimates. The maps are validated using hold-out field inventory data. The study reveals
17 that AGB ranges from 13 to 300 Mg/ha, with a mean of 93.69 Mg/ha, primarily concentrated
18 in grasslands (below 1000 meters). The aboveground biomass density point cloud from GEDI
19 LiDAR data, modelled and upscaled using multi-sensor remote sensing datasets, reveals
20 biomass density patterns and tree species dynamics conforming to the regional patterns. The

21 findings underscore the importance of elevation and forest cover type in hosting dominant
22 portions of AGCS in Kudremukh National Park. This work offers valuable insights into
23 carbon stock assessment and ecosystem dynamics, benefiting policy decisions related to
24 climate change mitigation and biodiversity conservation efforts.

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27 **Keywords:** Biomass, Above-Ground Carbon Stocks (AGCS), LiDAR, SAR, Multispectral
28 data, Machine Learning, Random Forests, Western Ghats, Biodiversity

29

30 1 INTRODUCTION

31

32 Forests are vital as wildlife habitats, clean water, sources of materials and commodities, as
33 well as carbon sinks.¹ Carbon storage and sequestration are among the most important
34 services forest ecosystems provide, which are important factors for climate change mitigation
35 and adaptation. However, their value is not always adequately recognized, with people often
36 taking for granted the benefits of the forest ecosystems.^{2,3} Studies have estimated that up to
37 20% of annual greenhouse gas emissions are caused by the loss of forests due to natural and
38 anthropogenic disturbances worldwide.⁴ Therefore, accurately estimating carbon levels is
39 crucial for biodiversity conservation and climate mitigation efforts. Concerns about the
40 effects of increasing atmospheric carbon dioxide on climate have spurred an international
41 initiative aimed at reducing forest-related emissions, notably in the tropics, where the bulk of
42 global deforestation occurs.⁵ The implementation of Reducing Emissions from Deforestation
43 and Forest Degradation (REDD+) hinges on the ability to monitor forest carbon stock and
44 dynamics across spatial scales, ranging from entire countries down to the localized scales
45 where deforestation and degradation processes occur.⁶

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47 The Western Ghats is a global biodiversity hotspot for numeric endemic species and
48 a wide variety of habitats including as streams, wet evergreen forests, grasslands, scrub
49 forests, savannas, peat bogs, Myristica swamps, and man-made habitats.^{7,8} It serves as a
50 significant carbon reservoir, actively sequestering atmospheric CO₂ and mitigating climate
51 change. Encompassing 36% of the protected areas in India, the Western Ghats harbour
52 diverse forest ecosystems, including tropical rainforests, evergreen, and deciduous forests,
53 with an estimated vegetation carbon stock of 1.23 Gt (billion gigagrams).⁹ Functionally
54 relevant and high-resolution mapping of the carbon sequestration potential of the Western
55 Ghats is crucial for understanding the localized patterns of climate change, water, and food
56 security in peninsular India.^{9,10} The Kudremukh National Park (KNP), one of the UNESCO
57 World Heritage sites in Western Ghats,¹¹ is considered representative of the gross ecological
58 and biodiversity characteristics of the Western Ghats. It is an indicator of substantial tropical
59 biological diversity with a high rate of endemism and is the region of the origin of three
60 major rivers - Tunga, Bhadra, and Netravathi rivers. The distinctive evergreen ecosystem
61 within the park plays a crucial role in executing various regulatory functions, particularly
62 regarding biogeochemical cycles. This unique ecological system efficiently manages and
63 influences the flow of essential elements, demonstrating its significance in maintaining
64 ecological balance and sustainability. The records of the forest department of the Government
65 of Karnataka¹² illustrate that the landscape of Kudremukh National Park has undergone
66 considerable changes during the last four decades. Holding the world's largest iron ore
67 deposits, mining activities were initiated from 1980 identifying mineralized areas of about
68 500 ha. In the process of establishing the unit, the entire landscape of the area was modified
69 with a huge township and other infrastructure facilities. The environmental impact
70 assessment of mining, which was carried out 20 years after the establishment of iron ore

71 mining and processing factor, has highlighted several adverse impacts of mining on the local
72 ecology¹³ and eventually led to the declaration of it a protected national park in 1987 and
73 banning of mining activities in 2005.¹⁴

74

75 The forest department, mining authorities, and a number of other corporates involved
76 in the mining and plantation businesses have carried out extensive plantations using exotic
77 trees such as *Eucalyptus tereticornis*, *Acacia auriculiformis*, *Grevillea robusta* and *Casuarina*
78 *equisetifolia*.^{12,15} Nevertheless, Kudremukh National Park structurally is heterogeneous and
79 has exceptionally high biological diversity. The degree of endemism is very high¹⁶ in
80 Kudremukh National Park, which includes *Poeciloneuron indicum*, *Myristica dactyloides*,
81 *Litsea floribunda* and many other species, and has the characteristics of relics. An accurate
82 estimation of forest aboveground biomass (AGB) is required to provide the baseline carbon
83 stocks and quantify the anthropogenic emissions caused by deforestation and forest
84 degradation in the context of Climate change.¹⁷ In addition, accurate estimation of forest
85 AGB density is critical for implementing cost-effective carbon emission mitigation strategies.
86 The conventional approach of AGB estimation relies on the allometric equations developed
87 based on limited field sampling of tree structural parameters such as height and diameter at
88 breast height (DBH).^{18,19} This conventional approach is valuable to a certain extent; however,
89 it is expensive and time-consuming over a vast forest area, limiting scalability. Furthermore,
90 field-based inventory and destructive biomass sampling approaches can introduce substantial
91 sampling and upscaling distortions.²⁰

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93 Remote sensing data allows large-scale assessments of the forest ecosystem,
94 structure, and functionality. Various studies have demonstrated the potential of estimating
95 biomass and other structural metrics of forest stands using data from optical,^{21,22} SAR,²³ and
96 LiDAR^{24,25,26,27,28} sensors mounted on ground-based, airborne, and space-borne platforms. A
97 range of methods, - statistical regressions,²¹ machine learning,²⁹ and deep learning,^{30,31} have
98 also been used for estimating the forest biomass. While optical imagery proves proficient in
99 delineating biomass variations, it reaches a point of saturation beyond which it is unable to
100 discern further biomass fluctuations.³² Conversely, LiDAR exhibits promise in generating
101 AGB density points; however, its sparse distribution of data points renders it inefficient for
102 comprehensive AGB density mapping across extensive areas due to its inherent limitations.²¹
103 Even though many studies have adopted integrated or data fusion methods to overcome the
104 limitations of using a single remote sensing datatype, the forest landscapes that represent the
105 data extents are often limited in spatial extent, and the forest landscapes are predominantly
106 homogeneous with similar terrain and ecological conditions across the length and breadth of
107 imagery coverage.^{27,33,34} Application of these studies to complex mosaics of landscapes like
108 Western Ghats is very limited. These constraints often limit the generalization or inference of
109 model suitability for carbon estimations over expansive areas in highly diversified forest
110 landscapes in tropical countries such as the Western Ghats of India. Except for the global or
111 biome-level maps of carbon estimates produced from coarse-resolution satellite data,^{23,31,35}
112 there are very limited attempts at assessing the methodological implementations and
113 application of multi-sensor remote sensing data for AGB estimation over a large area -
114 encompassing the full range of forest ecosystems and heterogeneity typical of the Western
115 Ghats of India and thereby serving as operational reference estimations of AGB.^{36,37}
116 Leveraging LiDAR and SAR data addresses saturation concerns, whereas optical imagery
117 facilitates scaling the data from regional to broader spatial scales. The objective of this study
118 is to estimate the AGB of a complex and heterogeneous forest landscape of the Western
119 Ghats of India by fusing optical, SAR, and LiDAR data in a machine-learning
120 methodological framework. Considering the space-borne LiDAR-based discrete estimates of

121 biomass as seed measurements, spatially continuous raster data from SAR and multispectral
122 satellite data were modelled by implementing a non-parametric ML approach, Random Forest
123 regression, for the generation of a spatially continuous and high-resolution AGB map that
124 encompasses the entire Kudremukh National Park of the Western Ghats of India. The AGB
125 estimates validated against field inventory values demonstrate consistent and reasonably high
126 accuracy in AGB mapping across varied spatial and ecological contexts.

2 MATERIALS AND METHODS

127 2.1 Study Area

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129 Within the broader context of generating AGB maps covering the entire geographical extent
130 of the Western Ghats, we have chosen a study site, Kudremukh National Park, which
131 represents geographical and ecological diversity of Western Ghats. The location map of the
132 study area is depicted in Figure 1. Kudremukh National Park extends between 75° 01' to 75°
133 25' E longitude and 13° 01' to 13° 29' N latitudes; found at an altitude of 1892 m above sea
134 level, encompassing forests of hilly terrain, in an area of 736.28 km² in the Western Ghats,
135 India. It includes Tungabhadra State Forest in the Chikkamagaluru Revenue District, the
136 Naravi reserve forest in the Dakshina Kannada district and the Andar reserve forest in the
137 Udupi District. The Kudremukh National Park has highland and lowland tropical evergreen
138 forests, shola, grassland, savannah, and mosaics of mixed semi-evergreen forest and
139 plantations in the peripheral area (Swamy and Procter, 1994; Krishnamurthy, 2003). The
140 climate is typically tropical, with annual rainfall ranging from 600 to 800 cm. The maximum
141 temperature varies from 21°C to 34°C during April–July, while the minimum temperature
142 ranges from 12°C to 18°C between January and May.^{15,38}

143

144 The landscape is a mosaic of several unique geographical, ecological, and social
145 attributes with changing elevations. The central, northern, and eastern parts of the study area
146 comprise a formation of rolling hills with a mosaic of grasslands and montane evergreen
147 forests.³⁹ The forest formation in the western slopes below 300 m are semi-evergreen in
148 nature and are influenced by anthropogenic activities. Below 200 m, a mosaic of landscape
149 element types replaces natural vegetation, with various types of plantations particularly,
150 Arecanut (*Areca catechu*) dominating this terrain.⁴⁰ Primary forest species are *Myristica*
151 *dactyloides*, *Palaquium ellipticum*, *Garcinia gummi-gutta*, and *Poeciloneuron indicum* play
152 crucial role in maintaining forest ecosystem stability and enhancing the provision of forest
153 ecosystem services.³⁸

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157 Figure 1. Study Area: location and administrative boundary of the Kudremukh National Park,
158 Western Ghats.
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161 2.2 Data Sources

162 The study used field inventory data and remote sensing data from different sensors.
163 Aboveground Biomass Density (AGBD) data points from GEDI, a satellite-based LiDAR
164 sensor, backscattering data from microwave RS satellite, multispectral satellite imagery and
165 DEM data form the primary RS datasets. Plot inventory data matching acquisition time and
166 geographical locations of the multi-sensor RS data considered were extracted from the series
167 of plot inventory data acquisitions carried out periodically under the National Carbon
168 Sequestration Mission, India. Below is a brief description of the sources of remote sensing
169 data used.

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171 2.2.1 Discrete measurements of aboveground biomass density (AGBD) from LiDAR

172

173 The Global Ecosystem Dynamics Investigation (GEDI) was a LiDAR mission launched by
174 NASA mounted on the International Space Station in 2018. This sensor was specifically
175 designed to retrieve vegetation structure within a novel, theoretical sampling design that
176 explicitly quantifies biomass and its uncertainty across various spatial scales.^{41,42} The GEDI
177 mission collected waveform LiDAR data with a dense sampling rate of ~25m footprint along
178 ground tracks paralleling the orbit of the International Space Station (ISS).⁴³ It provided 1 km
179 x 1 km estimates of mean aboveground biomass density (Mg ha^{-1}) based on observations
180 from mission week 19 starting 2019-04-18 to mission week 138 ending on 2021-08-04. The
181 GEDI L4A Footprint Biomass product converts each high-quality waveform to an AGBD
182 prediction. The L4B product uses the sample present within the borders of each 1 km cell to
183 statistically infer mean AGBD.⁴⁴ The mean aboveground biomass density layer of GEDI L4B
184 product was used in the study.

185

186 2.2.2 Multispectral and SAR Data and the computation of spectral indices

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188 The study used spatially continuous raster data from satellites - multispectral imagery from
 189 Sentinel-2, SAR imagery from Sentinel-1 and elevation data from SRTM DEM. The cloud-
 190 free imagery of Sentinel-2 and the corresponding Sentinel-1 data were procured for the year
 191 2021. The SAR data acquired from the Sentinel-1 are generally provided as Level-1 Ground
 192 Range Detected (GRD) products.⁴⁵ Using the SNAP toolbox provided by the European Space
 193 Agency,⁴⁶ the SAR data were processed for retrieving the geo-referenced backscatter
 194 coefficient (σ^0) in decibels (dB). Surface reflectance products from Sentinel-2 L2A images
 195 were composited as the S2 mosaic after the cloud and noise removal.^{47,48} To calculate
 196 topographic indicators SRTM DEM products were used.⁴⁹ Bringing to the desirable spatial
 197 resolution of 10m common in some spectral bands of Sentinel-2 and multiple spatial
 198 resolutions in Sentinel-1, the spatial resolution of the multispectral and SAR data was
 199 resampled to a uniform grid size of 10m. To match point-to-point elevation values, the DEM
 200 product was up-sampled from 30 m to 10m using the nearest neighbourhood approach. The
 201 data sets, and various products and indices generated for the study are listed in Table 1.
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Table 1. Multi-sensor variables used for Above Ground Biomass modelling.

Sl. No.	Images	Features	Description	
1	S1 mosaic	Backscatter	VV	Single co-polarisation, vertical transmit/vertical receive (in dB)
			VH	Dual-band cross-polarisation, vertical transmit/horizontal receive (in dB)
2	S2 mosaic	Multispectral Bands	B2*	Blue, 490 nm
			B3*	Green, 560 nm
			B4*	Red, 665 nm
			B5*	Red Edge 1/Visible and Near Infrared (VNIR), 705 nm
			B6	Red Edge 2/Visible and Near Infrared (VNIR), 740 nm
			B7	Red Edge 3/ Visible and Near Infrared (VNIR), 783 nm
			B8	Visible and Near Infrared (VNIR), 842 nm
			B8A	Visible and Near Infrared (VNIR), 865 nm
			B11*	Short Wave Infrared (SWIR), 1610 nm
			B12*	Short Wave Infrared (SWIR), 2190 nm
		Vegetation indices	RVI*	Ratio vegetation index, B8/B4
			DVI	Difference vegetation index, B8 – B4
			NDVI*	Normalised difference vegetation index, (B8 – B4)/(B8 + B4)
			EVI*	Enhanced vegetation index, $2.5 \times (B8 - B4)/(B8 + 6 \times B4 - 7.5 \times B2 + 1)$
S2REP	Sentinel-2 red-edge position index, $705 + 35 \times [(B4 + B7)/2 - B5] \times (B6 - B5)$			
REIP*	Red-edge inflection point index,			

				$700 + 40 \times [(B4 + B7)/2 - B5]/(B6 - B5)$
			SAVI*	Soil adjusted vegetation index, $1.5 \times (B8 - B4)/8 \times (B8 + B4 + 0.5)$
			MTCI*	Meris terrestrial chlorophyll index, $(B6 - B5)/(B5 - B4)$
			MCARI*	Modified chlorophyll absorption ratio index, $[(B5 - B4) - 0.2 \times (B5 - B3)] \times$ $(B5 - B4)$
			NDVI45*	Normalised difference vegetation index with bands 4 and 5, $(B5 - B4)/(B5 + B4)$
			NDVI56*	Normalised difference vegetation index with bands 5 and 6, $(B6 - B5)/(B6 + B5)$
			NDVI57	Normalised difference vegetation index with bands 5 and 7, $(B7 - B5)/(B7 + B5)$
			NDVI58a	Normalised difference vegetation index with bands 5 and 8a, $(B8a - B5)/(B8a +$ $B5)$
			NDVI67*	Normalised difference vegetation index with bands 6 and 7, $(B7 - B6)/(B7 + B6)$
			NDVI68a	Normalised difference vegetation index with bands 6 and 8a, $(B8a - B6)/(B8a +$ $B6)$
			NDVI78a	Normalized difference vegetation index with bands 7 and 8a, $(B8a - B7)/(B8a +$ $B7)$
3	SRTM	Topographic Indicators	Elevation*	Elevation in m
			Slope (β)*	Slope
			Aspect	Aspect
			Surface roughness	Surface roughness, $1/\cos \beta$

205 *Filtered predictor variables based on Random Forest variable importance,
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208 2.2.2 Ground truth data

209 The reference field biomass estimates were obtained using the volume and wood density of
210 each tree species by substituting tree diameter values from 2018 to 2020 following the
211 method suggested by the Forest Survey of India.⁵⁰ A plot measuring 1ha (100m x100m), sub-
212 divided into 25 quadrants of 0.04 ha each, was established as the standard measurement unit.
213 The plot's direction was set to true north and was precision geo-located using a differential
214 global navigation satellite system (DGNSS) receiver. Total station was used for marking
215 20x20 meter quadrant on the ground, and measurements were acquired in 10 quadrants within
216 each plot. The Quadrants were identified based on stratified random sampling and
217 accessibility. Plot-level biomass measurements were derived by upscaling the sampled
218 quadrants. The list of parameters measured in each quadrant are listed in Table 2. For several
219 sampling plots, Terrestrial Laser scanning (TLS) derived tree measurements were generated
220 to account for the non-availability of a few tree-specific parameters and to calibrate local
221 allometric equations. At each site, multiple scans-based TLS measurements were conducted
222 over four circular plots with a radius of 20m. To ensure inter-comparison and calibration of
223 the estimations, TLS scans were undertaken at some sites were full tree measurements and

224 equations are available. Estimations of tree parameters from TLS modelling³⁶ are considered
 225 field data equivalent. Distributed across the range of AGB variability in the study area,
 226 reference data on AGB and other tree parameters were acquired at 100 measurement plots.

227

228 Table 2. Summary of the parameters measured at reference plots during ground truth data
 229 acquisitions.

Sl. No.	Parameter	Instrument
1	Height	Leica Distometer S910
2	Diameter at Breast Height (DBH)	Meter tape
3	Leaf Area Index (LAI)	Licor LAI Meter2200
4	Fraction of Photosynthetically Active Radiation (fPAR)	Quantum Sensor
5	Species name/family	Taxonomist
6	Frequency	Manual counting
7	Bark/stem Sampling (FSI volume equations)	As permitted; manually chopping off selected pieces of stem/ Collection from a nearby timber depot

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231 2.3 Method for the Estimation of AGBD and Carbon Stocks and Validation

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233 The overall methodological framework used to estimate Above Ground Biomass Density
 234 (AGBD) and Carbon stock is given in Figure 2. For the complementary feature level fusion
 235 of remote sensing data from different sensors and for calibrating a model for estimating
 236 AGB, we used the Random Forests machine learning (ML) algorithm in the regression mode.
 237 Numerous ML algorithms are available in the literature,^{51,52} differentiated for their
 238 computational performance, ability to handle random and categorical variables, level of
 239 expert involvement, etc. Based on the relevant literature and our pre-implementation
 240 experiments for the selection of an appropriate ML algorithms, Random Forests (RF),
 241 amongst a host of ML algorithms such as Support Vector Machines (SVM), Multinomial
 242 Logistics Regression (MLR), Naive Bayes, K-Nearest Neighbours, Gradient Boosting (GB),
 243 AdaBoosting (AB) has offered consistently higher performance. We, therefore, chose the RF
 244 algorithm for non-parametric integration and modelling of biomass using field inventory and
 245 multi-source remote sensing data.

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247 From the GEDI L4B dataset, 1,000 AGB density points were sampled, which were
 248 used for machine learning model training and map visualisation. Further, the training data
 249 were split into training and validation sets. The training dataset was partitioned into training
 250 (70%) and validation (30%). Further, to train and evaluate the RF algorithm, the model
 251 parameter “number of trees” was defined as 500 to make the model statistically robust. Then,
 252 the RF algorithm was executed in regression mode, considering the predictor variables,
 253 including Sentinel-1 and Sentinel-2 mosaic and SRTM data, targeting the mean aboveground
 254 biomass obtained from the GEDI L4B dataset. To analyse the model's performance, a
 255 variable importance test was performed to understand whether the predictors had more
 256 influence on the model. The correlation was assessed between predicted and observed data
 257 and Root-Mean Square Error (RMSE) was computed. To optimize the model further, the
 258 predictor variables having the least significance were filtered out based on the Gini Index⁵³
 259 (Figure 3) and the model was re-calibrated. The prediction model thus optimized was
 260 validated using hold-out ground truth measurements and the spatially continuous AGBD map
 261 was generated.

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Calculating carbon stock as biomass consists of multiplying the total biomass by a conversion factor representing the average carbon content in biomass. It is not possible to separate the different biomass components to account for variations in carbon content as a function of the biomass component. Therefore, the coefficient of 0.55 for the conversion of biomass to C offered by Ref⁵⁴ is generalised here to conversions from biomass to carbon stock: $C = 0.55 \times \text{biomass (Mg/ha)}$.⁵⁵ Further, to understand the distribution of carbon across the study area, its variation was studied across different land use classes and elevation gradients.

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Figure 2. Methodological framework for estimating aboveground biomass (AGB) and carbon stock using multi-sensor remote sensing data.

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Figure 3. The importance feature evaluation computed based on the Gini Index for implementing the Random Forests algorithm for the multi-sensor remote sensing data used in the AGB estimation (the features are abbreviated in Table 1).

3 Results, Analysis, and Discussion

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The validated results of AGB estimation are shown in Figures 4 and 5. The overall AGB of Kudremukh National Park varies between 261.68 to 48.94 Mg/ha (Figure 4), with a mean

286 AGB of 149.18 Mg/ha. A strong correlation is observed between the estimated and measured
 287 AGB, wherein the goodness of fit (R^2) is 0.86 (Fig. 5) with an RMSE value of 12.94 Mg/ha,
 288 less than 10% of the mean value. These estimates are good considering the study site's vast
 289 geographical area and diversity. The estimates provided by the model are not random, as
 290 confirmed by the F-test, and are statistically significant at a confidence level of 95%. To
 291 understand the response of the model developed to various levels of AGB, the residual plot is
 292 shown in Figure 6. As evident, the points are randomly dispersed, and there is no systematic
 293 pattern in the variations of the AGB residuals, suggesting no generic overestimation or
 294 underestimation in the model. Even Though there is a substantial underestimation of biomass
 295 at higher AGB levels, this pattern appears to be a random feature, as evident from the much
 296 higher-level biomass.
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 299 Figure 4. Aboveground Biomass (AGB) map of the Kudremukh National Park, Western
 300 Ghats, India, obtained from the ML-based modelling of multi-sensor remote sensing and field
 301 inventory data.

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 303 Figure 5. Comparison of the estimated and measured AGB of the Kudremukh National Park,
 304 Western Ghats, India.
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307 Figure 6. Residual plot of the AGB generated from the paired differences between the
308 estimated and measured AGB values.

309
310 The ML-based estimations reveal that the Aboveground Carbon stock (AGCS) ranges from
311 150 to 50 Mg/ha (Figure 6) with a mean of 93.69 Mg/ha. It can be observed that a major
312 portion of the protected area's AGCS ranges between 50.32 and 73.72 Mg/ha (37.93%),
313 which is majorly composed of grasslands. About 79.89% of the AGCS lies at less than
314 1000m elevation (Table 3). This is because the lower elevation has many denser and
315 continuous patches of forests consisting of moist evergreen, semi-evergreen, moist deciduous
316 and dry deciduous forests. As one moves towards higher elevations, the forests become
317 patchier and stunted in adapting to the harsh climatic conditions in higher elevations. Also,
318 the shallow soil profile in the higher elevations acts as one of the regulatory agents for tree
319 growth. Most land covers in higher elevations are grassland or rocky outcrops.

320
321 Table 3. Elevation-wise distribution of aboveground carbon stock across the Kudremukh
322 National Park, Western Ghats, India.

Sl. No	Elevation (m)	Area(ha)	Carbon Stock (Mg)	Carbon Stock (Mg/ha)	Carbon Stock (%)
1	<=1000	60352.76	5913361.47	97.98	79.89
2	1000-1200	11205.97	900189.22	80.33	12.16
3	1200-1400	5230.33	401859.89	76.83	5.43
4	1400-1600	1517.38	125283.72	82.57	1.69
5	>1600	693.56	61191.63	88.23	0.83
Total		79000	7401885.94	93.69	100

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324
325 Figure 6. Spatial distribution of the estimated Aboveground Carbon Stock (AGCS) across the
326 Kudremukh National Park, Western Ghats, India.

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328 The important wet evergreen forest species in high-altitude (above 1400m) include *Litsea*
329 *floribunda*, *Symplocos racemosa*, *Wendlandia thyrsoides* and others, contributing less than
330 3% of the carbon stock of the entire landscape. On the other hand, the low-altitude wet
331 evergreen forest (under 1200 m) hosts species such as *Syzygium hemisphericum*, *Hopea*
332 *canarensis*, *Myristica dactyloides*, *Persia macrantha*, *Palaquium ellipticum*, *Poeciloneuron*
333 *indicum*, *Garcinia gummi-gutta.*, contributing 92.05% of the total aboveground carbon stocks
334 of Kudremukh National Park (Table 4). Much of the landscape is covered by forest (66.26%)
335 and grasslands (23.41%) which contribute to 71.30% and 18.64% of AGCS, equivalent to
336 5302990.96 Mg (101.14 Mg/ha) and 1383075.78 Mg (74.68 Mg/ha) of the carbon stock
337 respectively. Plantations and croplands, with ~4% of the land cover, account for 212120.45
338 Mg (99.41 Mg/ha) and 62559.63 (89.47 Mg/ha), respectively. Other land uses, including
339 rocky outcrops, built-up, and waterbodies, contribute to 6.75% of the area. The vegetation in
340 this land use class contributes to 472066.9 Mg (85.13 Mg/ha) (Table 4).

341
342 Table 4. Land use/land cover (LULC) wise distribution of aboveground carbon stock across
343 the Kudremukh National Park, Western Ghats, India.

Sl. No.	LULC	Area		Carbon stock		
		ha	%	Mg	Mg/ha	%
1	Forest	52304.53	66.26	5290273.24	101.14	71.30
2	Grassland	18520.73	23.41	1383075.78	74.68	18.64
3	Plantation	2133.70	2.70	212120.45	99.41	2.86
4	Cropland	699.25	0.88	62559.63	89.47	0.84
5	Rocky outcrop	372.60	0.47	31404.53	84.29	0.42
6	Built up	1497.00	1.89	116281.66	77.68	1.57
7	Waterbody	3472.21	4.39	324380.71	93.42	4.37

Total	79000.00	100	7420096.00	93.94	100
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The earliest studies by Ref ⁵⁶ have identified that the climax vegetation of these forests is tropical evergreen with poorer localities of semi-evergreen as a sub-type and rare richer localities with *Poeciloneuron indicum* as the principal outcrop. Physiognomic stages, such as scrub, savanna, etc., are also seen. Three important forest types, viz., pre-montane, low-altitude evergreen and semi-evergreen, are also discernible. The difference in the AGCS of tree cover can be attributed to different forest types, elevation, forest age and historical disturbances such as selective felling or logging, forest fires, mining, and other anthropogenic activities. The spatial distribution of AGCS acts as a potential indicator for understanding the ecosystem services offered by the forest landscapes. The total carbon stock of Kudremukh National Park is 7401885.94 Mg.

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Geographically large-scale and high-resolution maps of carbon stocks are invaluable baseline information products for understanding the contributions and status of the dynamics of carbon-source sinks in ecologically fragile and geographically diverse biodiversity hotspots. Rich in biodiversity and exhibiting the extremes of species heterogeneities by various factors of forest landscape systems, global biodiversity hotspots have undergone unprecedented anthropogenic disturbances and biological transformations. Traditional field inventory and remote sensing data-based methods have been widely used for estimating proxy variables of carbon stock, such as biomass, canopy density, tree height, etc. Even though good accuracy is reported, most studies have considered either coarse resolution or limited geographical extents in the implementations. Thus, the model results and inferences are often not applicable to full-scale and highly heterogeneous forest ecosystems such as the Western Ghats of India. Aimed at contributing to the global research efforts of developing and demonstrating methods for large areas but sensitive to localised interactions of carbon estimations in forest ecological systems, we have undertaken this research assessing and demonstrating the potential of an ML-based multi-source remote sensing data approach for the aboveground carbon stock (AGCS) estimation over an entire national park (Kudremukh National Park), a functional representative of the Western Ghats of India. The study employed a comprehensive methodology integrating field inventory data with remote sensing data from various sensors to estimate the aboveground biomass (AGB) and carbon stocks in Kudremukh National Park. Utilising data from LiDAR (GEDI), SAR (Sentinel-1), multispectral imagery (Sentinel-2), DEM (SRTM), field-inventory measurements, and adopting an appropriate ML algorithm, the study has successfully demonstrated the prospect of generating high-resolution maps of AGB. The AGB estimates of the Kudremukh National Park range from 261.68 to 48.94 Mg/ha, with a mean of 149.18 Mg/ha. The estimation of AGCS reveals values ranging from 150 to 50 Mg/ha, with a mean of 93.69 Mg/ha.

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The study highlighted notable trends in carbon distribution, with most carbon stocks concentrated in forests below 1000m elevation, dominated by wet evergreen species. Forests at higher elevations exhibit lower carbon stocks due to patchier vegetation and harsher climatic conditions. Additionally, anthropogenic activities such as selective felling, logging, and mining contribute to the variations in the carbon stocks across different forest types and elevations. The results underscore the importance of understanding ecosystem services provided by forest landscapes, with carbon stock distribution as a crucial indicator. The total carbon stock estimation of 7,401,885.94 Mg offers valuable insights for conservation and management strategies in Kudremukh National Park.

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Despite the study's merits in providing accurate carbon stock estimates across varied spatial and ecological contexts, it has limitations. These limitations include potential biases in field inventory data, uncertainties in remote sensing data compatibilities, and generalising

393 conversion factors for biomass to carbon estimations. Nevertheless, the study's integrated
394 approach demonstrates its significance in advancing our understanding of forest carbon
395 dynamics. It underscores the importance of utilising multi-sensor remote sensing techniques
396 for comprehensive ecosystem assessments.

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398 **4 CONCLUSIONS**

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400 Large-area and high-resolution estimation and mapping of aboveground carbon stocks
401 (AGCS) of highly productive and ecological heterogeneous forest ecosystems is an
402 invaluable methodological and information resource for functional forest management.
403 Geographically covering an entire protected national park in the Western Ghats of India, this
404 study has implemented and analysed a method for AGCS estimation at 10m spatial resolution
405 by feature-level fusion of data from multiple but complementary remote sensors (LDAR,
406 SAR and multispectral sensors) in a machine learning methodological framework.
407 Considering biomass as the proxy variable, the distribution of AGCS across the landscape
408 addresses diversity, disturbance, and distribution of the tree species. Has also been analysed.
409 Integrated by the RF machine learning algorithm, the primary predictor variable, discrete
410 records of biomass density obtained from the space-borne LIDAR (GEDI L4b) datasets blend
411 seamlessly with other remote sensing datasets and appear as a viable alternative to traditional
412 field-based inventory methods. Compared with field inventory values, the estimates of AGB
413 from the methodology adopted are 86% accurate. They are responsive to the variation of
414 AGCS across heterogeneous landscapes with varied elevation, ecology, and geological
415 features. The study contributes valuable insights to carbon stock assessment and ecosystem
416 dynamics and recommends adapting the integration of GEDI LiDAR, Sentinel-1, Sentinel-2,
417 and SRTM datasets to generate detailed AGB maps and carbon stock estimates. The study
418 also recommends promoting interdisciplinary collaboration between forest researchers,
419 remote sensing experts, and policymakers to facilitate the translation of scientific findings
420 into practical applications for climate change mitigation and biodiversity conservation efforts.

421

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423

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430 **Disclosure Statement**

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447

448 **CRedit authorship contribution statement:**

449 Kavana R : Writing – original draft, review & editing, Methodology, Conceptualization,
450 Data Curation, Formal Analysis. Rao Rama Nidamanuri: Writing – review & editing,
451 Methodology, Conceptualization, Formal Analysis, Data Curation. B C Nagaraja: Writing –
452 review & editing, Conceptualization. Shrinidhi Ambinakudige: Writing – review & editing,
453 Conceptualization. All authors reviewed the manuscript

454

455 **Code and Data Availability Statement**

456 Data sharing is not applicable to this article, as no new data were created or analysed.

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459 **5 REFERENCES**

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